

ICT Needs and Preferences and the Prevalent ICT Features of the Department Heads of JBLFMU-Molo

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Abstract

This research study determined the Information and Communications Technology (ICT) needs and preferences and the prevalent ICT features of the department heads of JBLFMU-Molo. The respondents of the study were the entire 16 department heads of JBLFMU-Molo. The instrument used was designed by the researchers. Findings reveal that the ICT devices needed by the department heads, in relation to their associated works and responsibilities with respect to their offices, should have the following features: functionalities of creating, editing, and checking of documents, portable, and Internet connection capability. A tablet is such a device. It may be more beneficial if such a device has a variety of communication means and that a tablet with a subscriber identity module (SIM) slot is a better option. The prevailing ICT features seen by the department heads, which are associated to their works and responsibilities in their respective offices, support the choice of a tablet. A switch to the use of a tablet, and better with a SIM slot is recommended.

Introduction

Information and communications technology (ICT) brings fast and convenient ways of doing transactions. ICT combines the fields of information processing, computing technology, and communications technology that nowadays are seem to be inseparable. The benefits of ICT devices such as desktop personal computer (PC), laptop PC, tablet PC, and smartphone encompass almost all disciplines. Everyone may agree that desktop PCs serve good. Though it is not portable, the features of such ICT device are amazing. With the brilliant ideas of many people, however, capabilities of bigger ICT devices may be enjoyed even with the smaller ones.

With the belief of Samsung Electronics Philippines Corp. (SEPCO) and La Salle Green Hills (LSGH) that the use of tablet PC as a personal learning device may prepare the students well for life in an increasingly information-based economy and electronically networked society, they initiated a project of turning the old classrooms into high-technology zones—the Pearl project. It was made possible through the idea of Jun Lozada, an electronics engineer by training, who noticed that many students carried heavy bags that may contribute into the worsening of scoliosis if one suffers from it (Padilla, 2011).

As part of its continuing paperless program for the environment, the local government of Makati City equipped the City Council members with high-tech tablets with SIM. It is said that the iPad 2 tablets have replaced the laptops the councilors had been using during council sessions. Aside from increasing the efficiency and performance of council members, Mayor Jejomar Erwin S. Binay mentioned that the equipment upgrade was in line with the city's thrust for 'e-governance' that was initiated in 2007 by then local executive and now Vice President Jejomar C. Binay. The paperless program of the City Council, according to the mayor, is in line with the overall mission of the city government to help the country and the world lessen consumption of paper and save the earth (Paunan, 2011).

With the goal of transforming the learning environment for the digital age and aligning it with the needs of the connected generation, Dell came out with the "Connected Classrooms". This is to do away with blackboards, chalk, charts, and other traditional teaching aids. It is believed that the use of digital media in lessons and classroom discussions may encourage the students to become more creative and innovative. The following devices would make the "Connected Classroom" possible: S300wi Interactive Short-Throw Projector, Interwrite Workspace software, Latitude 2120 netbook or the Latitude XT2 tablet PC, and the Ergotron TeachWell Mobile Digital Platform, a mobile workstation (Evangelista, 2011).

The Foundation University (FU) in Dumaguete City prepared to start a program of using iPad, an Apple's revolutionary tablet PC, in teaching Math, English, and Science for the sophomore high school students. Through the said device, students will learn through digitized Philippine textbooks from Vibal Publishing House Inc. that started producing e-books (Pal, 2011).

With the aim of cutting down the government's expenditure on textbooks, the provincial government of Laguna streamlined a pilot testing in public high schools of the e-book readers, which will be locally branded as Rizal Tablets after the national hero Jose Rizal. Some 1,000 tablet PCs will be tried next school year among freshman students of Laguna Science National High School (LSNHS), University of the Philippines Rural High School, and one public high school from each of the four congressional districts in Laguna. Twenty to 30 teachers will also be trained for the test run. Neil Nocon, provincial board member and education committee chair said that it will be like a virtual library. Further, he said that if after evaluation, indeed the use of the tablet proves that it is cost-effective and equally beneficial it may promote the use of it in place of regular textbooks (Cinco, 2010).

Adhering to one of the JBLFMU's seven point agenda, that is "Sustained Technological Environment" and believing on the benefits of ICT, each unit of JBLFMU is continuously enhancing different transaction with the integration of ICT to ensure quality service to its stakeholders. It is a reality however, that the pace of ICT is so fast that new features are made available every now and then.

Conceptual Framework

Recognizing the pace of ICT, the researchers believe that there is a need to reexamine the ICT needs and preferences among the department heads based on the associated work and responsibilities of their respective offices. Determining their present ICT needs and preferences may help in recommending the more appropriate ICT devices to use. Each ICT device has its own distinguishing characteristics. An enhanced feature of a device however comes in conflict to a different feature.

Shankel (2011) describes some distinguishing characteristics of desktop, laptop, netbook, and tablet computer. As the name implies, the desktop computer is designed to rest on a desktop. Some of its types are the following. An all-in-one desktop computer like Apple iMac is sold with all components within the same casing as the central processing unit (CPU). A full size desktop computer separates the different components, and features a tower. A smaller version of a full size computer is called the compact desktop computer. According to Consumerreports.org, the full size desktop is the easiest type of desktop computer to repair and upgrade. Desktop computers can be built or constructed for particular purposes like a gaming desktop computer that is designed specifically for playing video games, and features a fast quad-core processor, a high quality graphics card and plenty of Random Access Memory (RAM).

Laptop computer on the other hand is portable as its main difference from the desktop computer. A laptop, unlike the desktop, can be plugged into a wall outlet or run off battery power. However, once the battery power is drained, the laptop needs to be recharged. The screen size of a laptop computer can range between 12 to 18 inches. If a laptop computer and desktop computer offer the exact same features and functions, the laptop would cost more.

A downsized version of a laptop computer based upon its size and function is the netbook computer. Typically, netbooks have screens that range between 10 to 12 inches. Netbooks weigh between two and three pounds. The

main function of a netbook computer is to browse the Web, although word processing can also be accomplished. Netbooks on the average have a slower response time than laptop computers.

Designed to be taken with you wherever you go is the tablet computer. It is even smaller than a laptop. Example of which is the Apple iPad. Like a laptop and desktop computer, the tablet computer has the ability to browse the Web, watch movies, play music and more. Some tablet computers also include built-in cameras allowing you to take photos, record HD video and place face-to-face phone calls. Depending on a model, table computers operate on battery life.

Yang (2011) differentiates laptop and tablet on the features of portability, functionality, and ease of use. Tablets are easy to whip out and so convenient to turn its screen on for reading or for quick browsing. Other tablets also have calling functionality which also eliminates the need for a phone. For those who need heavy-duty computing, here is where the tablet comes up short. Sacrificing essential ports and third-party hardware compatibility, like lack of USB ports for devices like hard drives, the tablet is more of a content-delivery device than a versatile working tool. While tablets are handy for quick e-mailing or annotating a contract, starting a long document from scratch or creating a spreadsheet may prove not only tedious but tiring on a tablet.

Smartphone on the other hand is a device that lets you make telephone calls and has additional features that, in the past, you would have found only on a personal digital assistant or a computer, such as the ability to send and receive e-mail and edit office documents (Cassavoy, 2012).

Figure 1 on the next page shows the conceptual framework of the study. The researchers believe that ICT needs and preferences may vary depending on the type of office where the department head belongs as well as depending one's sex. Further, with the conflicting features of ICT devices, prevailing ICT features among the department heads may also vary.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This research study determined the ICT needs and preferences and the prevalent ICT features of the department heads of JBLFMU-Molo. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What are the ICT needs and preferences of the department heads of JBLFMU-Molo when taken as a whole and when grouped according to (a) type of office and (b) sex?
2. From among the conflicting features of ICT devices, which features prevailed to the department heads of JBLFMU-Molo when taken as a whole and when grouped according to (a) type of office and (b) sex?

Significance of the Study

The researchers consider the results of this study important to the administration, staff, and students of JBLFMU-Molo.

The administration may consider enjoying the benefits of other ICT devices especially the new ones to keep abreast of the ICT technology. Such a consideration might lead to a better way of doing transactions in the campus.

The staff, including both the academic and non-academic personnel, may also consider reexamining their ICT needs and determine if a shift is necessary.

The students may acquire additional information about the school and the efforts of the administration for the betterment of doing transactions in the campus.

Scope and Limitations

This study was conducted during the second semester of the academic year 2011-2012. The respondents of the study were the entire 16 department heads of JBLFMU-Molo. The instrument used was designed by the researchers. In designing the instrument, only the following ICT devices were considered: desktop PC, laptop PC, netbook PC, tablet PC, and smartphone. Further, only the following features were considered: storage capacity, functionality, portability, ease of repair, cost, and telecommunication. Frequency, relative frequency (rounded off to the nearest ones), and mode were used in analyzing the data.

Methodology

This descriptive research aimed to determine the ICT needs and preferences and the prevailing ICT features among the department heads of the JBLFMU-Molo. A questionnaire was made by the researchers to gather data.

The questionnaire was made of three parts. The first part determines the type of office and sex of the respondent. The second part contains 10 items to determine the ICT needs and preferences. Each item has three choices. Each choice would correspond to a certain feature of ICT devices like desktop PC, laptop PC, netbook PC, tablet PC, and smartphone. The third part contains 10 items to determine the prevailing ICT features among the respondents. The items are paired based on the conflicting features of ICT devices. Each item has seven (7) choices. The nearest two (2) choices to either side confirm the choice from the conflicting feature, while the three (3) choices at the middle connotes the choice of an almost balance from the conflicting features. The instruction explicitly states that the respondent should answer based on the associated works and responsibilities of the office he/she belongs.

Since there are only 16 department heads at JBLFMU-Molo, all of them were considered as respondents. In regards to type of office, six (6) of them are in the non-academic offices, while 10 of them are under the academic offices. In regards to sex, 11 of them are male, while five (5) of them are female.

Each was given the questionnaire to answer. After collecting all the answered questionnaires, the data were processed. The frequency, relative frequency (percentage rounded off to the nearest ones), and mode were used to analyze the gathered data.

Results

The succeeding tables depict the ICT needs and preferences and the prevalent ICT features of the department heads of JBLFMU-Molo.

Table 1 shows the ICT needs and preferences of the department heads taken as a whole. In terms of the type of files being kept, majority (f=9, rf=56%) keeps files made more of texts. In terms of functionality, majority (f=6, rf=38%) performs either more of creating documents or more on editing and checking of documents. In terms of the extent of place where files kept require retrieval, majority (f=13, rf=81%) needs to access the files anywhere, even outside the campus. In terms of the extent of time work-related documents require retrieval, majority (f=9, rf=56%) needs to retrieve work-related documents anytime, even weekends. In terms of the urgency of fixing the ICT device should the device needs repair, majority (f=14, rf=88%) requires its immediate repair. Majority (f=11, rf=69%) is willing to accommodate work-related concerns anywhere, even when one is in a seminar outside the campus or even one is at home. Majority (f=8, rf=56%) is willing to accommodate work-related communications, may it be a call, text message, and the like anytime. Should personal money is required to spend for some work-related expenses, majority (f=12, rf=75%) is willing to spend a little amount. Majority (r=8, rf=50%) is either willing to try new methods or loves to explore in performing tasks. Majority (f=10, rf=63%) prefers a device that is about a foot-size.

Table 1
ICT Needs and Preferences among the Department Heads Taken as a Whole

ICT Needs and Preferences (N=16)	f	%
Type of files kept		
More of texts	9	56
Combination of texts, pictures, and videos	7	44
Computer tasks		
More of creating documents	6	38
More on editing and checking of documents	6	38
More on checking and viewing of documents	4	25
Extent of place to access files		
Anywhere (even outside the campus)	13	81
Within the campus	2	13
Within the designated office	1	6
Extent of time to retrieve work-related documents		
Anytime (even weekends)	9	56
A little extension outside the office hours	6	38
Within the office hours only	1	6
Urgency of fixing the device in relation to work-related concerns, should the device needs repair		
Immediate	14	88
Within a week	2	13
Extent of place one is willing to accommodate work-related concerns		
Anywhere (even at a seminar outside the campus and at home)	11	69
Within the campus	4	25
Within the office	1	6
Extent of time one is willing to accommodate work-related communications (call, text messages, and the like)		
Anytime	8	56
A little extension outside office hours	5	31
Office hours only	2	13
Amount of money one is willing to spend personally for some work-related expenses		
A little	12	75
Any amount	4	25
Preference in performing tasks		
Willing to try new methods	8	50
Explore	8	50
Preference on the size of display		
About a foot-size	10	63
Less than a foot-size	5	31
More than a foot-size	1	6

Table 2 shows the ICT needs and preferences among the department heads when grouped according to the type of office one belongs. In terms of the type of files being kept, majority (f=4, rf=67%) of those in the non-academic offices keeps files that combine texts, pictures, and videos, while majority (f=7, rf=70%) of those in the academic offices keeps files made more of texts only. In terms of functionality, majority (f=3, rf=50%) of those in the non-academic offices performs more of creating documents, while majority (f=4, rf=40%) of those in the academic offices performs more on editing and checking of documents. In terms of the extent of place where files kept require retrieval, all (f=6, rf=100%) in the non-academic offices and majority (f=7, rf=70%) in the academic offices need to access the files anywhere, even outside the campus. In terms of the extent of time work-related documents require retrieval, all (f=6, rf=100%) in the non-academic offices need to retrieve work-related documents anytime, even weekends, while majority (f=6, rf=60) in the academic offices needs to retrieve work-related documents a little extension outside of the office hours. In terms of the urgency of fixing the ICT device should the device needs repair, both majority in the non-academic offices (f=5, rf=83%) and in the academic offices (f=9, rf=90%) require its immediate repair. Both majority in the non-academic offices (f=4, rf=67%) and in the academic offices (f=7, rf=70%) are willing to accommodate work-related concerns anywhere, even when one is in a seminar outside the campus or even one is at home. Both majority in the non-academic offices (f=4, rf=67%) and in the academic offices (f=5, rf=50%) are willing to accommodate work-related communications, may it be a call, text message, and the like anytime. Should personal money is required to spend for some work-related expenses, both majority in the non-academic offices (f=5, rf=83%) and in the academic offices (f=7, rf=70%) are willing to spend a little amount. Majority (r=4, rf=67%) in the non-academic offices is willing to try new methods, while majority (f=6, rf=60%) in the academic offices loves to explore in performing tasks. Both majority in the non-academic offices (f=4, rf=67%) and in the academic offices (f=6, rf=60%) prefer a device that is about a foot-size.

Table 2
ICT Needs and Preferences among the Department Heads when Grouped according to the Type of Office

ICT Needs and Preferences	Non-Acad (N=6)		Acad (N=10)	
	f	%	f	%
Type of files kept				
Combination of texts, pictures, and videos	4	67	3	30
More of texts	2	33	7	70
Computer tasks				
More of creating documents	3	50	3	30
More on editing and checking of documents	2	33	4	40
More on checking and viewing of documents	1	17	3	30
Extent of place to access files				
Anywhere (even outside the campus)	6	100	7	70
Within the campus			2	20
Within the designated office			1	10
Extent of time to retrieve work-related documents				
Anytime (even weekends)	6	100	3	30
A little extension outside the office hours			6	60
Within the office hours only			1	10
Urgency of fixing the device in relation to work-related concerns, should the device needs repair				
Immediate	5	83	9	90
Within a week	1	17	1	10
Extent of place one is willing to accommodate work-related concerns				
Anywhere (even at a seminar outside the campus and at home)	4	67	7	70
Within the campus	2	33	2	20
Within the office			1	10
Extent of time one is willing to accommodate work-related communications (call, text messages, and the like)				
Anytime	4	67	5	50
A little extension outside office hours	1	17	4	40
Office hours only	1	17	1	10
Amount of money one is willing to spend personally for some work-related expenses				
A little	5	83	7	70
Any amount	1	17	3	30
Preference in performing tasks				
Willing to try new methods	4	67	4	40
Explore	2	33	6	60
Preference on the size of display				
About a foot-size	4	67	6	60
Less than a foot-size	2	33	3	30
More than a foot-size			1	10

Table 3 shows the ICT needs and preferences among the department heads when grouped according to sex. In terms of the type of files being kept,

majority (f=6, rf=55%) of the males keeps files that combine texts, pictures, and videos, while majority (f=4, rf=80%) of the females keeps files made more of texts only. In terms of functionality, majority (f=5, rf=45%) of the males performs more on editing and checking of documents, while majority (f=4, rf=40%) of the females performs more of creating documents. In terms of the extent of place where files kept require retrieval, both majority of the males (f=9, rf=92%) and females (f=4, rf=80%) need to access the files anywhere, even outside the campus. In terms of the extent of time work-related documents require retrieval, majority (f=5, rf=45%) of the males needs to retrieve work-related documents either anytime, even weekends or with a little extension outside the office hours, while majority (f=4, rf=80) of the females needs to retrieve work-related documents anytime, even weekends. In terms of the urgency of fixing the ICT device should the device needs repair, majority of the males (f=9, rf=82%) and all the females (f=5, rf=100%) require its immediate repair. Both majority of the males (f=7, rf=64%) and females (f=4, rf=80%) are willing to accommodate work-related concerns anywhere, even when one is in a seminar outside the campus or even one is at home. Both majority of the males (f=6, rf=55%) and females (f=3, rf=60%) are willing to accommodate work-related communications, may it be a call, text message, and the like anytime. Should personal money is required to spend for some work-related expenses, both majority of the males (f=9, rf=82%) and females (f=3, rf=60%) are willing to spend a little amount. Majority (r=6, rf=66%) of the males loves to explore in performing tasks, while majority (f=3, rf=60%) of the females is willing to try new methods to perform tasks. Both majority of the males (f=6, rf=55%) and females (f=4, rf=80%) prefer a device that is about a foot-size.

Table 3
ICT Needs and Preferences among the Department Heads when Grouped according to Sex

ICT Needs and Preferences	Male (N=11)		Female (N=5)	
	f	%	f	%
Type of files kept				
Combination of texts, pictures, and videos	6	55	1	20
More of texts	5	45	4	80
Computer tasks				
More on editing and checking of documents	5	45	1	20
More on checking and viewing of documents	4	36		
More of creating documents	2	18	4	80
Extent of place to access files				
Anywhere (even outside the campus)	9	92	4	80
Within the campus	1	9	1	20
Within the designated office	1	9		
Extent of time to retrieve work-related documents				
Anytime (even weekends)	5	45	4	80
A little extension outside the office hours	5	45	1	20
Within the office hours only	1	9		
Urgency of fixing the device in relation to work-related concerns, should the device needs repair				
Immediate	9	82	5	100
Within a week	2	18		
Extent of place one is willing to accommodate work-related concerns				
Anywhere (even at a seminar outside the campus and at home)	7	64	4	80
Within the campus	3	27	1	20
Within the office	1	9		
Extent of time one is willing to accommodate work-related communications (call, text messages, and the like)				
Anytime	6	55	3	60
A little extension outside office hours	3	27	2	40
Office hours only	2	18		
Amount of money one is willing to spend personally for some work-related expenses				
A little	9	82	3	60
Any amount	2	18	2	40
Preference in performing tasks				
Explore	6	55	2	40
Willing to try new methods	5	45	3	60
Preference on the size of display				
About a foot-size	6	55	4	80
Less than a foot-size	4	36	1	20
More than a foot-size	1	9		

Table 4 shows the prevailing ICT features among the department heads taken as a whole. A feature that allows files to be accessed anywhere despite

of limited storage capacity prevails (f=9, rf=56%). Although creating and editing of documents are difficult, as long as the access to documents is fast and easy prevails (f=9, rf=56%). Even the workplace be extended outside the designated office, as long as it is ergonomically better prevails (f=12, rf=75%). Even the liability extends because security also extends through personal safekeeping, it prevails (f=14, rf=88%). Despite of limited accessories available for the device, as long as it is easily repaired should be needed, prevails (f=7, rf=44%). A feature that allows full Internet access despite it entails extension of office hours prevails (f=11, rf=69%). A feature that allows full means of communication that include email, call, messenger, text message, etc. despite that it may mean inseparable personal life and work life prevails (f=11, rf=69%). A feature that allows continuity of work due to uninterrupted power supply even if it entails personal expense prevails (f=10, rf=63%). Despite of the complicated programs and features, as long as it provides opportunity to utilize modern technology, prevails (f=13, rf=81%). A feature that is more portable despite of a narrow display prevails (f=8, rf=50%).

Table 4
Prevailing ICT Features among the Department Heads Taken as a Whole

Conflicting ICT Features (N=16)	f	%
Storage AGAINST Accessibility of files		
Limited storage YET Files may be accessed anywhere	9	56
High storage YET Limited access to files	5	31
Balance	2	13
Accessibility of documents AGAINST Document tasks		
Fast and easy access YET Difficult to create and edit	9	56
Requires presence at the office YET Easy to create and edit	4	25
Balance	3	19
Ergonomics AGAINST Workplace		
Ergonomically better YET Workplace is extended outside	12	75
Balance	4	25
Ergonomically poor YET Workplace is within the office	0	0
Security AGAINST Liability		
Personal safekeeping YET Extended liability	14	88
Balance	1	6
Exposed to co-workers YET Limited liability	1	6
Accessories AGAINST Repair		
Limited accessories YET Easy to repair	7	44
Variety of accessories YET Repair is difficult	5	31
Balance	4	25
Internet Access AGAINST Office hours		
Full Internet access YET Office hours is extended	11	69
Limited Internet access YET Work within office hours only	4	25
Balance	1	6
Communication AGAINST Personal life		
Full means of communication YET Inseparable personal & work	11	69
Limited means of communication YET Separated personal & work	3	19
Balance	2	13
Continuity of work (on power supply) AGAINST Personal Expense		
Less interruption YET Entails personal expense	10	63
Balance	5	31
Prone to interruption YET Free from personal expense	1	6
Opportunity of Modern Technology AGAINST Ease of use		
Good opportunity YET Complicated features	13	81
Balance	2	13
Lesser opportunity YET Easy to use	1	6
Size of display AGAINST Portability		
Narrow display YET More portable	8	50
Wider display YET Less portable	4	25
Balance	4	25

Table 5 shows the prevailing ICT features among the department heads when grouped according to the type of office. A feature that allows files to be accessed anywhere despite of limited storage capacity prevails to both in the non-academic (f=4, rf=67%) and academic (f=5, rf=50%) offices. Although creating and editing of documents are difficult, as long as the access to documents is fast and easy prevails to both in the non-academic (f=4, rf=67%) and academic (f=5, rf=50%) offices. Even the workplace be extended outside the designated office, as long as it is ergonomically better, it prevails to both in the non-academic (f=5, rf=83%) and academic (f=7, rf=70%) offices. Even the liability extends because security also extends through personal safekeeping, it prevails to both in the non-academic (f=5, rf=83%) and academic (f=9, rf=90%) offices. A balance between the availability of accessories and ease of repair prevails (f=3, rf=50%) to those in the non-academic offices, while despite of limited accessories available for the device, as long as it is easily repaired should be needed prevails (f=6, rf=60%) for those in the academic offices. A feature that allows full Internet access despite it entails extension of office hours prevails to both in the non-academic (f=4, rf=67%) and academic (f=7, rf=70%) offices. A feature that allows full means of communication that include email, call, messenger, text message, etc. despite that it may mean inseparable personal life and work life prevails to both in the non-academic (f=3, rf=50%) and academic (f=8, rf=80%) offices. A feature either that allows continuity of work due to uninterrupted power supply even if it entails personal expense or a balance between the continuity of work and a personal expense prevails (f=3, rf=50%) to those in the non-academic offices, while a feature that allows continuity of work due to uninterrupted power supply even if it entails personal expense prevails (f=7, rf=70%) to those in the academic offices. Despite of the complicated programs and features, as long as it provides opportunity to utilize modern technology, prevails to both in the non-academic (f=5, rf=83%) and academic (f=8, rf=80%) offices. A balance between portability and size of display prevails (f=3, rf=50) to those in the non-academic offices, while a feature that is more portable despite of a narrow display prevails (f=6, rf=60%) to those in the academic offices.

Table 5
Prevailing ICT Features among the Department Heads when Grouped according to the Type of Office

Conflicting ICT Features	Non-Acad (N=6)		Acad (N=10)	
	f	%	f	%
Storage AGAINST Accessibility of files				
Limited storage YET Files may be accessed anywhere	4	67	5	50
High storage YET Limited access to files	1	17	4	40
Balance	1	17	1	10
Accessibility of documents AGAINST Document tasks				
Fast and easy access YET Difficult to create and edit	4	67	5	50
Requires presence at the office YET Easy to create and edit	1	17	3	30
Balance	1	17	2	20
Ergonomics AGAINST Workplace				
Ergonomically better YET Workplace is extended outside	5	83	7	70
Balance	1	17	3	30
Ergonomically poor YET Workplace is within the office	0	0	0	0
Security AGAINST Liability				
Personal safekeeping YET Extended liability	5	83	9	90
Balance	1	17	0	0
Exposed to co-workers YET Limited liability	0	0	1	10
Accessories AGAINST Repair				
Balance	3	50	1	10
Variety of accessories YET Repair is difficult	2	33	3	30
Limited accessories YET Easy to repair	1	17	6	60
Internet Access AGAINST Office hours				
Full Internet access YET Office hours is extended	4	67	7	70
Limited Internet access YET Work within office hours only	1	17	3	30
Balance	1	17	0	0
Communication AGAINST Personal life				
Full means of communication YET Inseparable personal & work	3	50	8	80
Limited means of communication YET Separated personal & work	2	33	1	10
Balance	1	17	1	10
Continuity of work (on power supply) AGAINST Personal Expense				
Less interruption YET Entails personal expense	3	50	7	70
Balance	3	50	2	20
Prone to interruption YET Free from personal expense	0	0	1	10
Opportunity of Modern Technology AGAINST Ease of use				
Good opportunity YET Complicated features	5	83	8	80
Balance	1	17	1	10
Lesser opportunity YET Easy to use	0	0	1	10
Size of display AGAINST Portability				
Balance	3	50	1	10
Narrow display YET More portable	2	33	6	60
Wider display YET Less portable	1	17	3	30

Table 6 shows the prevailing ICT features among the department heads when grouped according to sex. A feature that allows files to be accessed anywhere despite of limited storage capacity prevails to both the males (f=5, rf=45%) and females (f=4, rf=80%). Although creating and editing of documents are difficult, as long as the access to documents is fast and easy prevails to both the males (f=5, rf=45%) and females (f=4, rf=80%). Even the workplace be extended outside the designated office, as long as it is ergonomically better, it prevails to both the males (f=7, rf=64%) and females (f=5, rf=100%). Even the liability extends because security also extends through personal safekeeping, it prevails to both the males (f=9, rf=82%) and females (f=5, rf=100%). Despite of limited accessories available for the device, as long as it is easily repaired should be needed prevails (f=5, rf=45%) to the males, while the availability of varied accessories despite difficulty of repair prevails (f=3, rf=60%) to the females. A feature that allows full Internet access despite it entails extension of office hours prevails to both the males (f=6, rf=55%) and females (f=5, rf=100%). A feature that allows full means of communication that include email, call, messenger, text message, etc. despite that it may mean inseparable personal life and work life prevails to both the males (f=6, rf=55%) and females (f=5, rf=100%). A feature either that allows continuity of work due to uninterrupted power supply even if it entails personal expense or a balance between the continuity of work and personal expense prevails (f=5, rf=45%) to the males, while a feature that allows continuity of work due to uninterrupted power supply even if it entails personal expense prevails (f=5, rf=100%) to the females. Despite of the complicated programs and features, as long as it provides opportunity to utilize modern technology, prevails to both to the males (f=8, rf=73%) and females (f=5, rf=100%). Either a more portable despite of narrow display or a balance between portability and size of display prevails (f=4, rf=36) to the males, while a feature that is more portable despite of narrow display prevails (f=4, rf=80%) to the females.

Table 6
Prevailing ICT Features among the Department Heads when Grouped according to Sex

Conflicting ICT Features	Male (N=11)		Female (N=5)	
	f	%	f	%
Storage AGAINST Accessibility of files				
Limited storage YET Files may be accessed anywhere	5	45	4	80
High storage YET Limited access to files	4	36	1	20
Balance	2	18	0	0
Accessibility of documents AGAINST Document tasks				
Fast and easy access YET Difficult to create and edit	5	45	4	80
Requires presence at the office YET Easy to create and edit	3	27	1	20
Balance	3	27	0	0
Ergonomics AGAINST Workplace				
Ergonomically better YET Workplace is extended outside	7	64	5	100
Balance	4	36	0	0
Ergonomically poor YET Workplace is within the office	0	0	0	0
Security AGAINST Liability				
Personal safekeeping YET Extended liability	9	82	5	100
Balance	1	9	0	0
Exposed to co-workers YET Limited liability	1	9	0	0
Accessories AGAINST Repair				
Limited accessories YET Easy to repair	5	45	2	40
Balance	4	36	0	0
Variety of accessories YET Repair is difficult	2	18	3	60
Internet Access AGAINST Office hours				
Full Internet access YET Office hours is extended	6	55	5	100
Limited Internet access YET Work within office hours only	4	36	0	0
Balance	1	9	0	0
Communication AGAINST Personal life				
Full means of communication YET Inseparable personal & work	6	55	5	100
Limited means of communication YET Separated personal & work	3	27	0	0
Balance	2	18	0	0
Continuity of work (on power supply) AGAINST Personal Expense				
Less interruption YET Entails personal expense	5	45	5	100
Balance	5	45	0	0
Prone to interruption YET Free from personal expense	1	9	0	0
Opportunity of Modern Technology AGAINST Ease of use				
Good opportunity YET Complicated features	8	73	5	100
Balance	2	18	0	0
Lesser opportunity YET Easy to use	1	9	0	0
Size of display AGAINST Portability				
Narrow display YET More portable	4	36	4	80
Balance	4	36	0	0
Wider display YET Less portable	3	27	1	20

Conclusions

The associated works and responsibilities among the department heads of JBLFMU-Molo require ICT devices with the functionalities of creating, editing, and checking of documents. Such devices include a capability of accessing stored files anywhere. However, should problem arises, it must easily be repaired. Taking into considerations the goodness among the department heads through their willingness to accommodate work-related concerns anywhere, willingness to accommodate communications anytime, willingness to spend a little amount of money for some work-related expenses, preference of either trying new methods or exploring, and preference of about a foot-size display, a modern ICT devices may be considered. An ICT device that is portable and has a good feature for Internet connection like a tablet is suitable. It may be more beneficial if such a device has a variety of communication means. In this case, a tablet with SIM slot would be a better option.

The prevailing ICT features seen by the department heads, which are associated to their works and responsibilities in the respective offices they belong, support the choice of a tablet. However, there is a need of considering a good brand to ensure ease of repair should problem arises on the device.

Recommendations

The administration may consider the shift from non portable ICT devices to portable ones like a tablet, and better with a SIM slot. This maximizes the potentials of both the device and the personnel. Should a shift to portable ICT devices be considered, a review of the features of different brands has to be made to ensure the quality of the chosen devices. A study then on the effectiveness of such ICT devices is recommended.

A shift of ICT devices may also be considered in other services of the university, particularly the instruction. Like some of the schools in the Philippines, the use of tablets and other new ICT devices may be considered. A study on this field is recommended.

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